

New HORIZON2020 project for a safer Europe

PRECINCT

Damage or destruction of critical infrastructures by natural disasters, terrorism and criminal activity can have devastating consequences for the security of the EU and the well-being of its citizens. Emerging threats, as well as unconventional attacks to critical infrastructures have exposed the limits of traditional risk assessment and risk mitigation efforts. Therefore, a common cyber-physical security management approach is urgently necessary. The new project PRECINCT strives to develop such an approach.

Safer infrastructures are a priority for the EU

Improving resilience of critical infrastructures has become a priority for the EU authorities. Consequently, a new EU Horizon 2020 project has been founded. The ambitious project PRECINCT “Preparedness and Resilience Enforcement for Critical INfrastructure Cascading Cyberphysical Threats” and effects with focus on district or regional protection has recently started.

PRECINCT aims to connect private and public CI (Critical Infrastructure) stakeholders in a geographical area to a common cyber-physical security management approach which will yield a protected territory for citizens and infrastructures. The ultimate ambition is that PRECINCT can be replicated efficiently and effectively for a safer Europe.

PRECINCT in numbers

CIs representing the transport, water, energy and ICT sectors and law enforcement agencies are actively involved in shaping the project development, which cover different types of CIs (private/public), size and geographical distribution. 4 Living Labs will be set up and the concepts will be further validated in 3 Demonstrators in the EU and beyond, more than 20 CIs and first responders, national authorities will participate creating a critical mass for adoption. This work will provide a robust evidence base of which approaches, and technical solutions are working, and which components provide clear advantages. Altogether, the consortium consists of 40 partners of excellence from 11 countries with very cross-cutting and complementary competencies.

For more information, please contact:
www.precinct.info/en/contact

